

DEVELOPING SPEAKING SKILLS THROUGH READING WITH NEW APPROACHES AND TECHNOLOGIES IN ENGLISH

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ABSTRACT. There is an increasingly high relationship between reading and speaking skills. There is no question that people who develop large reading vocabularies tend to develop large speaking vocabularies. Indeed, reading power relies on continuous improvement in vocabulary knowledge that provides communication. The importance of word knowledge, which facilitates speaking skills, has been a major resource in the development of reading skills. Therefore fostering improvement in word knowledge through wide reading has the potential for fostering improvement in speaking skills. This article focuses on how printed words relate to spoken words and finally how reading contributes to speech.

KEYWORDS: reading skills, speaking skills, vocabulary knowledge, modern technologies, enhancing Speaking Skill.

INTRODUCTION. “Where there is little reading there will be little language learning. ... the student who wants to learn English will have to read himself into a knowledge of it unless he can move into an English environment” (Bright and McGregor, 1970, p.52). Language acquisition without reading is difficult. Reading is a good way of comprehension. A good reader is able to understand sentences and structures of a written text. Bright and McGregor are of the opinion that reading is ‘the most pleasant route to command of the language’, because it is via reading ‘the student is most likely to find words used memorably with force and point.’(1970, p.53). It appears that reading is a key factor in language learning. One important notion of developing reading skills and speaking skills is to use the language for learning as well as communication. Reading can play a big part in successful language learning. It can develop speaking skills. It needs to be noted that speaking holds a very significant place in foreign language learning because through speech messages are conveyed. According to Ur (1996, p.120), “of all the four skills (listening, speaking, reading and writing), speaking seems intuitively the most important”. Reading outside the classroom is the most significant influence on oral communication ability. Students who read a lot are more likely to speak well. Students through reading develop in both

fluency and accuracy of expression in their speaking. Davies and Pearse (2000) stresses the importance of communication as: “Real success in English teaching and learning is when the learners can actually communicate in English inside and outside the classroom.”

READING. Reading is one of the most effective ways of foreign language learning. Reading simply is the interpretation of a written message. Walter R. Hill (1979, p.4) briefly defines reading as what the reader does to get the meaning he needs from contextual resources. Reading is a fluent process of readers combining information from a text and their own background knowledge to build meaning and the goal of reading is comprehension (Nunan, 2003, p.68). The ability to read requires that the reader draw information from a text and combine it with information and expectations that the reader already has (Grabe, Stoller, 2001, p.187). Alderson J.C. (2000) states that reading is built from two components: word recognition and comprehension. These two components gained through reading will foster learners’ language competence. Krashen and Terrell (1989, p.131) point out that reading enables learners to comprehend better which is an important factor that can develop language competence.

Hedge (2003) writes the goals of learners’ in a reading process as:

- The ability to read a wide range of texts in English.
- Building a knowledge of language which will facilitate reading ability
- Building schematic knowledge
- The ability to adapt the reading style according to reading purpose (skimming, scanning)
 - Developing an awareness of the structure of written texts in English
 - Taking a critical stance to the contexts of the texts

Reading will add to learners’ conversational performance. Reading will help learners to decipher new words that they need for conversations. Through reading language learners will have vocabulary knowledge which will facilitate their speaking performance and their usage of structure in the target language will develop. These components which are required through reading are all necessary for developing speaking skills. Similarly, Williams (1984, p.13) suggests some reasons why language learners should read in a foreign language:

- Learners can have further practice in the language that they have learnt,
- Learners can practice language in order to reuse it in other skills such as speaking and writing,
- Learners can learn how to get benefit from the texts to extract the information they need,

- Learners can find enjoyment or interest through reading.

Integrating Reading and Speaking Skills In a reading process six component skills have been suggested. Among these knowledge fields vocabulary and structural knowledge which are acquired through reading, influence learner's speaking achievement.

- 1) Automatic recognition skills
- 2) Vocabulary and structural knowledge
- 3) Formal discourse structure knowledge
- 4) Content/world background knowledge
- 5) Synthesis and evaluation skills/strategies
- 6) Metacognitive knowledge and skills monitoring (Grabe,1991, p.379).

How do these component skills contribute to speaking skills? Anne Lazaraton (2001, p.104) suggests that oral communication is based on four dimensions or competences: grammatical competence (phonology, vocabulary, word and sentence formation ...); sociolinguistic competence (rules for interaction, social meanings); discourse competence (cohesion and how sentences are linked together); and strategic competence (compensatory strategies to use in difficult strategies).

Vocabulary knowledge and grammar are two essential factors of foreign language learning, and they both influence learner's speaking performance. Good knowledge of grammar is viewed as an essential aspect for achievement in a foreign language. Grammar is important to learn the nature of language. Grammar helps learners to build comprehensible sentences in speaking. In order to understand how language works, learners should give attention to grammar. "If we only understand what others say partially and superficially, the communication of ideas can't be properly realized (Zhong-guo, Min-yan, 2007, p.63)." Reading will help learners acquire vocabulary and grammar. Through reading learners see how words fit together. When learners constantly engage in the target language, they begin noticing and mastering the patterns in the language. Mccarthy (2000) states that lexical and grammatical knowledge are significantly correlated to reading comprehension. This means learners will achieve better reading comprehension through grammar. Krashen (cited in Hill and Holden, 1990, p.92) encourages reading because it is a great factor in foreign language improvement and believes that students who read a lot are good at reading, good at writing and have a good vocabulary and grammar knowledge. Learners see structure of a sentence and this enables them to build their own sentences and utterances.

Of all four key language skills, speaking is deemed to be the most important in learning a second or foreign language. As stated by Ur (1996), speaking included all other skills of knowing that language. Speaking is "the process of building and sharing meaning through the use of verbal and non-verbal symbols, in a variety of contexts" (Chaney, 1998). Speaking is a crucial part of second language learning and teaching, it's an art of communications and one of 4 productive skills, that must be mastered in learning foreign language. Good speaking skills are the act of generating words that can be understood by listeners. According to Brown and Yule (1983), speaking is the skill that the students will be judged upon most in real-life situations. It is an important part of everyday interaction and most often the first impression of a person is based on his/her ability to speak fluently and comprehensively. So, teachers have a responsibility to prepare the students as much as possible to be able to speak in English in the real world outside the classroom. Despite its importance, for many years, teaching speaking has been undervalued and English language teachers have continued to teach speaking just as a repetition of drills or memorization of dialogues. However, today's world requires that the goal of teaching speaking should improve students' communicative skills, because, only in that way, students can express themselves and learn how to follow the social and cultural rules appropriate in each communicative circumstance. In the preliminary stage, teachers used tape recorders as a technological device to instruct the students, which later evolved as communication laboratory. The integration of technology into language teaching which was started in the early 1960s and 1970s, assisted teachers to teach second language learners how to speak in the best way possible. Every day teachers are getting access to some new technologies, which join hand with English teaching. As the conventional teaching method such as the chalk and talk method seems to be outdated, the modern technologies can be used as a supplement to the classroom teaching method to have a lively atmosphere in the classroom. It is the need of the hour to integrate modern technologies to upgrade the level of English teaching. The modern technologies relax the mind of the students to get into the subject with full involvement rather than a difficult task to do. New technologies in language learning by multiple intelligence and mixed abilities replace with old methods of teaching.

MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN DEVELOPING SPEAKING SKILL.

Technology can stimulate the playfulness of learners and immerse them in a variety of scenarios. Technology gives learners a chance to engage in self-directed actions, opportunities for self-paced interactions, privacy, and a safe environment in which errors get corrected and specific feedback is given. Feedback by a machine offers additional value by its ability to track mistakes and link the student immediately to

exercises that focus on specific errors. Studies are emerging that show the importance of qualitative feedback in softwares. When links are provided to locate explanations, additional help, and reference, the value of technology is further augmented. Modern technologies available in education today are:

- o Communication lab
- o Speech recognition software
- o Internet
- o TELL (Technology Enhanced Language Learning)
- o Pod casting
- o Quick Link Pen
- o Quicktionary

HOW TO USE THESE TECHNOLOGIES: COMMUNICATION LABS.

Software's are available to develop speaking skills. By incorporating suitable software through computers the students will play it again and again with their own interest and try to improve their speaking skills, which are most essential in this modernized IT world. The usage of headphones in the lab makes the students to have interest over the subject and induces them to repeat again and again instead of feeling boredom.

SPEECH RECOGNITION SOFTWARE. Speech recognition software also helps improving the students speaking, this can convert spoken words to machine-readable input. The device recognizes the accuracy of what was read and then provides a positive reinforcement like "You sound great!" or gives the user an opportunity to try again, in this way the learner can figure if he is reading well or not. As the user's skill improves, the technology reads less material so that the learner reads more. This software also evaluates and provides scores of grammar, pronunciation, comprehension and provided with the correct forms, for examples if a student mispronounces a word, the learning tool can immediately spot it and help correct it. This device can be a very useful device for distance learners because they don't have a teacher who corrects their speech and this device can help improving their speaking skills.

INTERNET. Internet is a commonly acknowledged term and widely used by people throughout the world. Students now use Internet in the class to learn English. Online teaching inside the classroom seems to be interesting and makes the students to find out the suitable materials for them. Students are instructed to do the grammar exercises which are available online. Through Internet we can collect data from various sources for any instruction. to improve speaking, students can use Skype, MSM Messenger, Google talk (used to have conferences on line) and other applications where students can connect with friends, other students, teacher and even native

speakers, these ways of learning have been observed to improve oral proficiency in students and make up for the lack of native speakers in the areas where students live and what is more, on line conferences also enhance intercultural awareness, motivation and raise the level of interaction. Over the internet, students can find a lot of learning materials, for instance, audio, video, radio and TV shows, games, voice recordings, quizzes, podcasts and so on , in this way, students get exposed to a great amount of target language and this help them develop their speaking skills.

TELL. Tell is the use of computer technology including hardware, software and the internet to enhance teaching and learning of languages. It allows the students to get access with all the technologies available for the enhancement of English learning. Students are allowed to use online dictionaries, chat, and to view the various happenings around the world.

POD CASTING. Podcasts can be uploaded or downloaded, this audio help the learner familiarize with the target language and teachers can use them as useful audio material that can be used in class for activities like discussions, besides, in the web, there are even particular podcasts that are for ESL learners and these can include pronunciation for particular needs of students. Podcast undoubtedly help learners in speaking. Pod casting is the integration of audio files where we can feed our own materials and ply it inside and outside of the classroom. Students use i-pods to hear their favorite music files. In the same way they have their education in the form of entertainment. Podcasting allows students to use their tech-based entertainment systems for educational purposes. With it we are able to move away from the traditional face-to-face training without losing the student-to-trainer relationship that is so effective in any learning process. Podcasts enables students and teachers to share information with anyone at anytime. An absent student can download the podcast of recorded lesson and is able to access the missed lectures. They could also access lectures of experts which may not otherwise be available because of geographical distance and other reasons.

QUICK LINK PEN. Quick Link Pen allows learners to copy and store printed text, Internet links. It helps to transfer the data to computers and enables the reader to get the meaning of the word from a built in dictionary. Accessing this type of machine seems to be a more convenient method. Recent developments in machine translations presents translation engines like GO Translator and Bablefish.

QUICKTIONARY. It is a pen-like device. It allows the reader to easily scan the word and get its definition and translation on its own LCD screen. Technology such as Enounce and Sound-Editor enable learners to adjust the speech rate of listening materials to assist their comprehension, and present spectrum of speech waves and

visual depictions of mouth and tongue movement to ease the learning and refine pronunciation.

In the theoretical model of L1 and L2 speaking (Levelt, 1989, 1993), vocabulary has a central position in forming an utterance with appropriate meanings and with syntactic, morphological, and phonological structures. Levelt's model suggests two points. First, vocabulary is always required in the formulation stage. In other words, no speech can be produced without vocabulary, and vocabulary is indispensable to speaking performance. Second, the lexicon consisting of lemmas and lexemes includes not only vocabulary size (i.e., primary meaning and form [phonology]) but also depth (i.e., syntax and morphology), which suggests that both size and depth are related to speaking performance (adapted from Rie Koizumi, 2005, p.53). The study by Adams (1980) and Higgs and Clifford (1982) indicates close relationships between vocabulary as part of overall speaking performance and overall speaking performance at low levels than at intermediate and advance levels (adapted from Koizumi, 2005, p.53). For spoken English the best reading materials are dramas, plays and dialogues. Learners have the opportunity to find sentences and phrases used in our daily conversation in dramas, plays and dialogues because they are all based on one person talking to another. Some studies have shown that using authentic texts has a positive effect on learning the target language by developing communicative competence (Peacock, 1997). "A text is usually regarded as authentic if it is not written for teaching purposes but for a real-life communicative purpose, where the writer has a certain message to pass on to the reader. As such, an authentic text is one that possesses an intrinsically communicative quality" (Lee, 1995). It is real language created by native speakers of the target language in pursuit of communicative outcomes (Little, Devitt, & Singleton, 1989). Integrating speaking and reading skills deepens students' understanding of the reading material, reveals any problem they have understanding a text, and, most importantly, lets them apply the information they have read into authentic speaking practice that improves their fluency (Zhang, 2009, p.34).

CONCLUSIONS. Communication without vocabulary will break down. One of the most useful ways to improve your communication skills is extensive reading. Extensive reading will help you to develop your ability to express ideas, whilst also enlarging the size of vocabulary. Vocabulary knowledge is one of the crucial factors that will influence fluency in speaking. Reading introduces learners to a wider body of language and contexts. Reading helps learners build up better grammar skills. As learners develop stronger reading skills, they develop more sophisticated speaking skills. Using technology in learning a second language has become a real necessity nowadays. This paper has reviewed briefly how technology can be utilized in

developing the speaking skill of the learners. Different methods for using technology in improving speaking skill were discussed thoroughly. As a result, the following concluding remarks and recommendations can be recorded: 1. As technology has developed the incorporation of this medium into the instruction process become necessary.

2. The computer is being viewed more as an integral part of the learning activity, and as a means by which skills are transferred to learners.

3. Theory and practice in second language learning can be matched together by the use of modern technology.

4. Modern technical ways should be followed for effective learning and teaching of the speaking skill.

5. English language teachers should encourage their students to use technology in developing their speaking skill.

6. Educational institutions should modernize their technical instruction capabilities by using new equipments and laboratories for supporting the teaching process.

7. Modern technological tools are much more interesting and provide fun and enjoyable learning, motivating the students, and help them to enhance their language learning in a fruitful way, moreover, these tools help students learn at their own pace and promote autonomy in them

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